

Cassiopeia's Secret

RUDOLF ARNOLD, EMU ENSEMBLE / MUSISCHES ZENTRUM /
UNIVERSITY OF ULM

1. PROGRAM NOTES

The performance 'Cassiopeia's Secret' is a first approach to an artistic, emotional, and scientific examination of the relations between music, sexology, gender identity, and astrophysics. It utilizes medical sensors and the technique of sonification to make sexual arousal audible. Moreover, there are tactile stimulators controlled by music and data generated by cosmic phenomena. The sensors and vibrators are hidden beneath a futuristic attire called a Pleasure Space Suit designed for sexual relaxation during long space travels. The story is about an experiment performed by Cassiopeia, a genderfluid Space Girl wearing the Pleasure Suit, and her friend and scientist, Dr. Aurélie. It is a simulated mission to an exomoon where the audience perceives the sonification of Cassiopeia's sexual arousal, the sound of celestial signals, and Aurélie's stimulating music as a futuristic symphony of pleasure.

Fig. 1. First Pleasure Space Suit Prototype.

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). Copyright remains with the author(s).

DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/0000000.0000000>
Music Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression
NIME'24, 4–6 September, 2024, Utrecht, The Netherlands

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Can music convey sexual arousal? Can orgasms made audible? Without vocalizing? You might say, of course! Many composers have done this. Just think about Richard Wagner's 'Isoldes Liebestod' [1].

'Cassiopeia's Secret' will be very different: it will be live, uninhibited, and experimental in a provocative manner. It is based on vibrotactile stimulation of erogenous zones and employs real-time sonification of biosignals directly related to sexual arousal. Besides standard signals like pulse, galvanic skin response, and breath, pelvic muscle tension is used because it is a reliable indicator of sexual arousal and orgasm induced by vibrotactile stimulation of erogenous zones [2]. It is essential to say that measuring pelvic muscle tension is gender-neutral in contrast to vaginal blood flow or penile erection. Here, muscle tension is measured with a small anal probe. The base structure is 3D printed, and the shaft is surrounded by a coiled silicone tube [Fig. 2]. The tube is attached to a pressure sensor connected to an Arduino-compatible microprocessor board. The probe is the most essential component of a system for the sonification of sexual arousal [3]. It is a medical sensor, not a sex toy.

Fig. 2. Anal Probe with Pressure Sensor.

'Cassiopeia's Secret' is breaking taboos! The taboo to make sexual acts a central topic of live performances. The taboo to make the sensual human body a tactile interface of musical expression of gender identity. The taboo of intimacy with non-human entities such as celestial bodies. The enactment does this without explicit action, nudity, vocalization, or dirty talking. The whole story unfolds in the realm of sound and music, creating extraterrestrial erotic fantasies.

Cassiopeia's secret is the deep longing of a genderfluid spacegirl for intimacy with celestial bodies. It's their sexual relationship with her friend and scientist, Aurélie.

It's the desire to express their gender identity through music. This is facilitated by a specialized attire, their Pleasure Space Suit [Fig. 1]. The prototype was inspired by the needs of a new scientific field called Space Sexology [4].

This specialized skintight catsuit, called 'Cosmic Caresse,' has various vibrotactile stimulators for diverse erogenous zones and sensors for biosignals like heart rate, skin response, and breath. It also has this unique gender-neutral medical sensor [Fig. 2], described above, to measure pelvic muscle tension directly related to tactile sexual arousal [3]. The readings are fed into a system of Arduino-compatible devices, distributed using the OSC protocol, and sonified by programs like SuperCollider or Max/MSP to convert them into music in real time [3].

However, music is not only used to make psychophysiological reactions audible. It is also employed to manipulate the speed and patterns of the vibrators hidden beneath the surface of the Pleasure Space Suit [3]. When a passionate musician plays the controlling instrument, such as a synthesizer, they can convey love, tenderness, sensuality, and lust to their beloved wearing the suit. Finally, combining music from both sources creates a thrilling symphony of bliss [Fig. 3].

Fig. 3. Stimulation and Sonification Loop

The principle is simple: music controls vibrators, vibrators increase sexual arousal, and sexual arousal leads to higher pelvic muscle tension, which is measured and transformed into the pitch [Fig. 4] and other parameters of computer-generated sound. Thus, the human body becomes an erotic musical instrument driven by tactile stimulation.

The performance portrays Cassiopeia as the subject of an experiment conducted at a fictional space medicine hub. It is a test of the Pleasure Space Suit during a simulated mission to the Exomoon Iphis. Dr. Aurélie, her girlfriend and principal investigator at the Space Girl Science Academy, supervises the virtual flight from a remote location many kilometers away [Fig. 5]. Aurélie plays a futuristic musical instrument that activates and manipulates the stimulators underneath Cassiopeia's catsuit.

Fig. 4. Mapping of Sexual Arousal and Orgasm to Pitch

But Aurélie not only plays her lust organ to stimulate Cassiopeia. She also introduces the sonification of cosmic signals. This way, Cassiopeia’s dreams come true as they build an intimate relationship with space and turn their gender identity as a femme-identifying androgynous spacegirl into otherworldly music.

Fig.5. Simplified Scheme

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

The erotic character of the performance makes Nijverheid the ideal venue. It will last less than 15 minutes. When staged at other venues, it will last 8 minutes.

The sexual content of the performance must be announced so that visitors who feel uncomfortable with the topic can leave the venue for a break.

The leading performer acts on stage, the second abroad or in a corner of the stage

Venue requirements:

Internet

Fast Internet Connection with Wi-Fi Router. Firewall port activations: Triggering 57100 UDP 57100–57120, Triggering 9000 UDP 9000-9010.

Audio

2 XLR connections to the audio system of the venue with a potent subwoofer

Video

2 HDMI connections to two projectors from the venue

Furniture

Mobile lab cart with power extensions connected to the power supply of the venue

Flight simulator gaming seat with seat belts

Lighting

One spot from back above

Equipment brought by the performer:

Pleasure Space Suit prototype, Notebook, several Arduino boards, three Raspberry Pi, a local Wi-Fi access point, a MIDI keyboard, and a small audio mixer.

4. MEDIA LINK(S)

- Video: <https://vimeo.com/942964945>

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author would like to thank Lovatron, EMU Ensemble, SEADS Collective, Dr. S. Gruß, and J. Seidl.

ETHICAL STANDARDS

The performance does not involve research on people or animals. It does not include offending action and nudity. Sexual stimulation and arousal are only induced and perceived by music and musical sonification. The content of the performance will be announced, and visitors who feel uncomfortable can leave the venue for a break. Thus, no ethical standards are violated.

REFERENCES

- [1] Mahnkopf, Claus Steffen (2019). Philosophie des Orgasmus. Suhrkamp, p127.
- [2] Gillan, P., Brindley G.S. (1979). Vaginal and Pelvic Floor Responses to Sexual Stimulation. *Psychophysiology* 16(5).
- [3] Arnold, R. (2020). PLAY ME: Interactive sonification of sexual arousal in long-distance relationships. *Paladyn, Journal of Behavioral Robotics*, 11(1), 250-270.
- [4] Dubé, S. et al., (2023). The Case for Space Sexology. *The Journal of Sex Research*, 60(2), 165-176.